
Information Seeking Approach of Paramedical & Nursing Professional in Aizawl, Mizoram: A Study

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Abstract

The present paper discussed about the information needs and seeking approach of Paramedical and Nursing Professional in Aizawl, Mizoram. The study is based on survey method and Questionnaire method was used to carried out the study. The population of this study was 141 paramedical and nursing professional. The findings of the study revealed that paramedical and nursing professional mostly need information for teaching, research, clinical works, caretaking of patients, problems of patients, new medical trends and health policies and self-development where they are dealing with students, different people and needed to up-to-date. The study found that majority of the professionals consult printed materials, web-based/electronic form and discussion with Librarian/reference staff of library and reviewing of articles. And held conversations with medical experts, colleagues, and patients for seeking information.

Keywords

Information Seeking; Nursing Professional; Strategy

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of "Information Seeking Approach" refers to the way users seek and utilise information. It relates to the method or procedure used to look for the data. Individual approaches of information seeking differ based on the kind of data they require. Therefore, the ability to identify the types of information required, the objectives or goals, and the relevant information sources to utilise all lead to information seeking activity. It also describes the process of obtaining seeking for information, signifying that after identifying the kind of information is required, an individual utilises their preferred ways to find it from a variety of sources, whether it be a basic or complex search. All information sources and channels-related activities, including proactive and reactive information.

OVERVIEW OF PARAMEDICAL & NURSING INSTITUTION IN AIZAWL, MIZORAM

Aizawl is the capital city and the most populous city of Mizoram, India. It is also the fourth largest city in northeast India, after Agartala and Imphal. It is situated atop a series of ridges, with an average elevation of around 1,132 metres (3,714 feet) above sea level. In 2024, the city has an estimated population of 405,000 people. Despite being merely 21,081 square kilometres in size. There are a lot of well-known elementary, middle, high, and college institutions. Each of the state's 10 nursing institutions is vital to its growth and healthcare infrastructure.

Table 1 List of Paramedical & Nursing Institution in Aizawl

Sl.No	Name of Institution	Established year	Courses offer	No. of faculty
1	RIPANS (Regional Institute)	1994	B.Sc Nursing, B.Optometric, B.Sc RIT, B.Sc MLT, B.Pharm	50
	Mizoram College of Nursing	1990	B.Sc Nursing	21
3	Synod Nursing College	1936	B.Sc Nursing	13
4	BN College of Nursing	2020	B.Sc Nursing	13

5	Apollo Nursing School	2005	General Nursing & Midwifery (GNM)	7
6	Blessino Nursing School	2019	General Nursing & Midwifery (GNM)	10
7	Health Worker Training Institute, Kulikawn	1957	Auxiliary Nurse & Midwife	10
8	Auxiliary Nursing Midwife School, Zemabawk	2021	Auxiliary Nurse & Midwife	5
9	Mission Foundation Movement	2009	Auxiliary Nurse & Midwife	5
10	Aizawl College of Nursing	2024	B.Sc Nursing	7

ROLE OF PROFESSIONALS WHILE APPROACHING INFORMATION SEEKING

Knowledge is becoming multidimensional in the digital age, as such professionals need to reconsolidate their position, redesign their services, incorporate new technologies and upgrade information resources. They should play a proactive role in harnessing the information to satisfy the needs of students and upgrade information resources. For the strength and success of a profession, professional education plays a vital role. In the fast changing scenario it is important to discuss and delivery on this important subject. As research and teaching increasingly rely on global networks for the creation, storage and dissemination of knowledge, the need to educate information-literate students has become more widely recognized. Students frequently lack the abilities needed to thrive in this quickly evolving environment, and teachers require assistance and training in order to effectively employ new technology for instruction. Professionals have an opportunity to assist significantly to the development of an integrated information literacy curriculum in the present context.

NEED OF INFORMATION

Most of the current, scholarly and commercial information is now on line. Tremendous growth in the number and variety of online digital information resources i.e.:- Electronic versions of traditional scholarly publications like journals and increasing number of free, quality content made the librarians to acquire and maintain digital materials in their library. This arises the Librarians to do increasing need for “Personalization” of information packaging and delivery. Significant use and preference for, online resources by students, teachers and researchers. Their expectation for improved access to electronic information continues to grow. Through this we will get instant access to a wide range of multimedia digital information sources of the world. And improved internal communication and access to internal information.

SKILLS REQUIRED FOR INFORMATION PROFESSIONALS

An ideal information professional must possess the following abilities:-

- : Suitable subject knowledge of the parent organization.
- An understanding of the information sources and users.
- Good communication skills
- Intermediary. Take a query and provide a "packaged" answer, drawing on a range
 - Appropriate subject-matter expertise of the parent entity.
- An understanding of the information sources and users.
- Good communication skills
- An understanding of the information sources and users.
- Good communication skills
 - A knowledge of the users and sources of information, as well as efficient communication skills.
- Intermediary. Take a query and provide a "packaged" answer, drawing on a range
 - Intermediary - Using a variety of sources, including print, online bibliographic databases, and the Internet, deliver a "packaged" response to a question.
- Guide. Provide pointers to aid user in search, critical evaluation of relevant
 - Provide guidance and pointers to help the user look for and critically assess appropriate sources.

- Facilitator - Organise the information infrastructure, including software, network access, and licenses for the use of paid resources, assist users utilise the databases.
- Instructor - Give instruction on how to use the Internet, including its tools, information-searching techniques, and resource-constrained awareness. Notify users of fresh resources related to their topic. Educating students on how to evaluate online sources critically.
- Builder for websites - Overview of Web-Based Educational Resources.
- Find, assess, and provide links to informational resources that are pertinent to the organisation. Providing a specific Internet service.
- Describe the library or information service on the Internet (website).
- Utilise information abilities to give a campus-wide information system or intranet and manage the organization's relevant information on the website.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sateesha (2023) highlights the importance of libraries for post-graduate students studying engineering, medicine, and social science, as they often struggle to find enough books, reference materials, and internet connections. Libraries should focus on providing more physically referable, innovative papers and raising awareness to support student skill development. Wanyingi (2023) found that nursing and clinical students visit libraries for electronic resources, periodicals, and textbooks, but their information demands are not fully satisfied. The study suggests that libraries should collaborate with students and provide all necessary resources. Akram (2021) found that paramedics need knowledge to stay current in the medical field and answer questions during clinical decisions. They also need access to health information for clinical practice, patient care, new medical trends, patient issues, medication awareness, societal issues, and self-improvement. They obtain information through books, dictionaries, research papers, newspapers, and periodicals, as well as speaking with patients, coworkers, and medical specialists.

Miraj (2021) explored how certain underlying causes may increase students' academic achievements, with information seeking, IT ability, reading/writing

capacity, and resilience being key factors. The findings showed that information seeking has a positive and significant impact on academic performance, with IT skills significantly improving it. Writing and reading also had an immense impact on academic achievement. Ammentorp (2014) found that convenience, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness are key elements influencing non-nursing college students' lived experiences when searching for health information online. To prevent confusion and worry, care must be used while assessing the authenticity and dependability of information obtained online. Stakeholders like legislators, medical professionals, and educators can create focused interventions and educational programs to improve students' experiences seeking health information, strengthen their critical evaluation abilities, and encourage the use of health information.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study's methodology is survey research, and data from respondents was gathered using a standardised questionnaire. Questionnaire has been distributed to all professionals of nursing institutions in Aizawl, Mizoram. A total 141 questionnaire was circulated to all professionals. Out of 141 questionnaire, 112 (79.43%) responses were collected, and MS Excel was used to analyse the data.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

a) Profile of Faculty

Table 2 :Gender-wise analysis

Sl. No	Gender	No. of Faculty	Percentage
1	Male	19	16.96%
2	Female	93	83.03%
	Total	112	100%

Table 2's data indicates that in Aizawl, majority of the nursing faculties are female where 93 female and 19 male make up the 112 faculty members in total.

b) Faculty Designation

Table 3 :Faculty Designation

Sl. No	Designation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Asst. Professor	28	25%
2	Tutor	84	75%
	Total	112	100%

From the above table we can see that majority of faculty members are tutors, with 84 (75%) and Assistant Professors, with 28 (25%) responding.

c) Faculty Qualification

Table 4:Faculty Qualification

Sl. No	Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Master	85	75%
2	Bachelor	27	24%
	Total	112	100%

Table 4's data indicates that in Aizawl, majority of the nursing faculties who hold Master degree are 85 (75%) while Bachelor degree are 27 (24%).

d) Library facilities

Table 5 :Library facilities

Sl. No	Library facilities	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Adequate	60	53%
2	Inadequate	52	46%
	Total	112	100%

From Table 5, it can be clearly see that majority of the faculty 53% are satisfied with the library facilities while 46% of professionals indicates that library facilities are inadequate.

e) Source of Information

Table 6 Source of Information

Sl. No	Name of Institution	Print	Electronic/ Web-based	Workshop/ Seminar	Discussion with Librarian/	Review Articles	No. of respondents
1	RIPANS (Regional Institute of Paramedical and Nursing Sciences)	15(44.11%)	10 (29.41%)	5 (14.70%)	0	4(11.76%)	34
2	Mizoram College of Nursing	5(33.33%)	8 (53.33%)	0	1(6.66%)	1(6.66%)	15
3	Synod Nursing College	6 (54.54%)	5 (45.45%)	0	0	0	11
4	BN College of Nursing	8 (61.53%)	4 (30.76%)	0	1(7.69%)	-	13
5	Aizawl College of Nursing	5 (71.42%)	2 (28.57%)	0	0	0	7
6	Apollo Nursing School	5 (71.42%)	2 (28.57%)	0	0	0	7
7	Blessino Nursing School	6 (60.00%)	2 (20.00%)	1(10.00%)	0	1(10.00%)	10
8	Health Worker Training Institute, Kulikawn	4 (80.00%)	1 (20.00%)	0	0	0	5
9	Auxiliary Nursing Midwife School, Zemabawk	5 (100%)	0	0	0	0	5
10	Mission Foundation Movement, Durtlang	3 (60.00%)	2 (40.00%)	0	0	0	5
	Total	62 (55.35%)	36 (32.14%)	6 (5.35%)	2 (1.78%)	6 (5.35%)	112

The above table shows the source of information by the nursing professionals in Aizawl, Mizoram.

Faculties are using several materials for teaching and learning such as Print material, Web-based/Electronic form and Discussion with Librarian/reference staff of library and Reviewing of Articles. The analysis shows that Printed material is the mostly used by the faculty 62

(55.35%). 36 (32.14%) of the faculty were using Electronic/Web-based followed by Workshop/Seminar and Review Articles 6 (5.35%) each. While 2 (1.78%) of the faculty were having Discussion with Librarian/reference staff of library.

f) Information Material Seeking in School/College of Nursing

Table 7 Materials seeking in School/College library

Sl. No	Name of Institution	Text Books	Periodicals	Govt. Publications	Reference books	Thesis/ Research Reports	No. of Respondents
1	RIPANS (Regional Institute of Paramedical and Nursing Sciences)	10 (29.41%)	3(8.82%)	3(8.82%)	14	4 (41.17%)	34
2	Mizoram College of Nursing	9 (60.00%)	0	0	4(26.66%)	2 (13.33%)	15
3	Synod Nursing College	7 (63.63%)	1(9.09%)	0	3(27.27%)	0	11
4	BN College of Nursing	7 (53.84%)	0	0	3(23.07%)	3 (23.07%)	13
5	Aizawl College of Nursing	5	0	0	2	0	7
6	Apollo Nursing School	5 (71.42%)	0	0	2(28.57%)	0	7
7	Blessino Nursing School	5 (50.00%)	2(20.00%)	0	3(30.00%)	0	10
8	Health Worker Training Institute, Kulikawn	4 (80.00%)	1(20.00%)	0	0	0	5
9	Auxiliary Nursing Midwife School, Zemabawk	3(60.00%)	1 (20.00%)	1(20.00%)	0	0	5
10	Mission Foundation Movement, Durtlang	3 (60.00%)	0	0	2(40.00%)	0	5
	Total	58(51.78%)	8 (7.14%)	4 (3.57%)	33(29.46%)	9 (8.03%)	112

From the above Table 7 we can clearly see that majority of the faculty 58 (51.78%) access Textbooks in the library where there are adequate number of collections. 33 (29.46%) of the faculty access Reference books in the library for teaching and learning. 9 (8.03%) of the faculty access Thesis/Research Report for teaching, learning and

research. 8 (7.14%) access Periodicals and 4 (3.57%) access Govt. Publication.

FINDINGS

In Aizawl, women make up the majority of the staff in nursing and paramedical facilities. The majority of faculty members are satisfied with the library's

resources. The majority of faculty members prefer printed materials, although some also use electronic or web-based resources, which are followed by workshop/seminar and review articles. Additionally, discussing with the Librarian and reference staff. Because the library has an adequate number of collections for teaching, learning, and research, professionals primarily visit it for textbooks. It might be argued that printed books performed the most important role and cannot be ignored by everyone in the rapidly evolving technological landscape, where everyone has access to the internet, even in remote locations. For teaching, learning, and research, reading printed information is more obvious than utilizing an electronic device.

CONCLUSION

Information is vital to the professional development of every learner and is crucial to the advancement of both the nation and its society. It is regarded as the society's resources. Every human activity entails it, and information is becoming more and more valuable. It is also regarded as a vital resource for human advancement. For any human activity to flourish, communication and knowledge are also required and they are linked to information. Without communication and knowledge, information cannot exist on its own. Thus, it is equally crucial to the development of the nation and the community. Thus, it is unable to disagree with the importance of knowledge, communication, and information. Information, which is the result of the functions of the human brain, is power. It is the information that is beneficial to making decisions and required for all actions, such as planning, development, research, and cultural endeavors. As a result, the need for knowledge among scientists, planners, decision-makers, educators, and researchers is growing quickly. This is an approach to increase the scope of medical care for patients and efficiently fulfill societal obligations in order to create a better society. One of the most significant tasks and obligations is providing patients with appropriate medical treatment, which may be achieved through appropriate information collecting. The library of the relevant institution must also construct resources and offer services. In addition to offering materials to nursing and paramedical workers, the library's duty extends to helping patients find solutions to their problems and make efficient use of their time. In the current ICT environment, libraries must improve their

services by enabling paramedical professional's access to the most appropriate material via the intranet. To boost the performance level of paramedical professionals in Mizoram, the medical environment needs to evolve, especially in the libraries. Additionally, efforts must be made to establish a brand for the institutes.

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